

Geometry optimization and thermodynamic stabilities of Zn^{II} mixed ligand complexes with salicylaldehyde and substituted salicylaldehydes

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Abstract : PM3 calculations have been carried out on Zn^{II} mixed ligand complexes Zn(sal)(5-Clisal), Zn(sal)(5-Brsal), Zn(sal)(5-NO₂sal), Zn(5-Clisal)(5-Brsal), Zn(5-Clisal)(5-NO₂sal) and Zn(5-Brsal)(5-NO₂sal) and the corresponding ligands and their bis-complexes Zn(sal)₂, Zn(5-Clisal)₂, Zn(5-Brsal)₂ and Zn(5-NO₂sal)₂. Thermodynamic stabilities based on heats of formation, total energies, ionization potentials, atom electron densities and atomic charges have been calculated. Geometry optimization of the complexes has been carried out on the basis of bond lengths and bond angles data. O-Zn-O bond angles are close to 109.5° (100.95° to 116.68°) suggesting distorted tetrahedral geometry for the complexes.

Keywords : PM3 method, zinc complexes, thermodynamic stability, geometry optimization.

Introduction

PM3 method¹ which is based on the Neglect of Differential Diatomic Overlap (NDDO) integral approximation has been parameterized for a large number of elements, including transition metals and has been widely used for rapid estimation of molecular properties and for geometry optimization of large number of transition metal complexes²⁻⁷. AM1⁸, PM3^{9,10} and MNDO/d^{11,12} have been applied for various studies on zinc-containing systems. The construction of 2 : 2 supramolecular box assemblies based on a bis-Zn^{II}-salphen building block and various ditopic bipyridine ligands has been investigated by Kleij *et al.*¹³ with the help of NMR, UV-Vis spectroscopy and X-ray crystallography and the strong interaction between the Zn^{II} center and pyridine donors was supported by PM3 calculations. PM3 calculations have been used for geometry optimization of the dehydrated Zn^{II} acetate¹⁴ and for determination of total and relative ligand binding energies, deprotonation energies of ligands and active sites of zinc containing biomolecules¹⁵. Synthesis and spectral studies of the mixed ligand complexes of Zn^{II} of the type ZnLL' (where L = 5-bromo and 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde and L' = acetylacetone, benzoylacetone and dibenzoylmethane) have been reported earlier from our laboratories^{16,17} and in the present paper the results of the PM3 calculations for thermody-

amic stabilities and geometry optimization of such type of complexes using MOPAC 2006 and MOPAC 6.0 are described.

Methodology :

With the help of softwares MOPAC 2006 and MOPAC 6.0 PM3 calculations for Zn^{II} complexes have been carried out. Using software MOPAC 2006 heats of formation, total energies, ionization potentials, atom electron densities and atomic charges for the Zn^{II} complexes have been calculated and bond lengths and bond angles have been determined with the help of MOPAC 6.0 software.

MOPAC 2006 : The structures of the complexes are drawn in Chemdraw ultra 8.0 and after giving keywords MOP file is prepared and the dos file is prepared by giving its keywords in RUN program. This dos file is run in software MOPAC 2006 and on completion, the output file containing the data of the following parameters is obtained : Heats of formation, Total energies, Ionization potentials, Atom electron densities, Atomic charges.

The MOP file is converted into PDB file through molecular structure file converter and the structures of the complexes are seen in Chem 3D.

MOPAC 6.0 : The structures of the complexes are drawn in PH₄ program of Serena software and notepad

file is prepared by giving keywords. This notepad is run in MOPAC software by giving its path and on completion the output file containing the data of bond lengths and bond angles is obtained.

Results and discussion

PM3 calculations have been carried out for Zn^{II} mixed ligand complexes Zn(sal)(5-ClSal), Zn(sal)(5-BrSal), Zn(sal)(5-NO₂sal)₂, Zn(5-ClSal)(5-BrSal), Zn(5-ClSal)(5-NO₂sal) and Zn(5-BrSal)(5-NO₂sal) and corresponding bis-complexes Zn(sal)₂, Zn(5-ClSal)₂, Zn(5-BrSal)₂ and Zn(5-NO₂sal)₂ (Fig. 1) and various parameters such as heats of formation, total energies, ionization potentials, atom electron densities, atomic charges, bond lengths and bond angles have been calculated.

Fig. 1. Structure of Zn^{II} complexes with salicylaldehyde and substituted salicylaldehydes.

Thermodynamic stabilities :

Heats of formation and total energies : The heat of formation of a molecule is a measure of its internal energy. The molecules with a positive heat of formation are less stable thermodynamically than the elements from which they are formed and those with negative heat of formation are more stable. For mixed ligand and bis-complexes of Zn^{II} with salicylaldehyde and substituted salicylaldehydes the heats of formation are negative quantities (-64.5016 to -27.6971 kcal, Table 1). On the basis

of the heats of formation of the complexes the following order of thermodynamic stability can be suggested : Zn(5-NO₂sal)₂ > Zn(5-ClSal)(5-NO₂sal) > Zn(5-ClSal)₂ > Zn(sal)(5-NO₂sal) > Zn(sal)(5-ClSal) > Zn(5-BrSal)(5-NO₂sal) > Zn(sal)₂ > Zn(5-ClSal)(5-BrSal) > Zn(sal)(5-BrSal) > Zn(5-BrSal)₂.

Effect of substituents : The order of thermodynamic stability of complexes can be explained on the basis of inductive (I) and mesomeric (M) effects shown by substituent groups of the ligands on the benzene ring. NO₂ group shows -I and -M effects both of which work in the same direction and enhance the effect, due to which the benzene ring becomes electron deficient hence the reactivity of ring decreases and stability increases. Thus, the complex Zn(5-NO₂sal)₂ is thermodynamically most stable. The chloro and bromo groups show -I and +M effects which work in the opposite directions but -I effect dominates the +M effect, hence it deactivates the benzene ring by creating electron deficiency in the ring, as a result of which stability increases. Hence, on this basis, the complex Zn(5-ClSal)₂ has greater thermodynamic stability and comes at third position in the stability order. However, the complex Zn(5-ClSal)(5-NO₂sal) is more stable than Zn(5-ClSal)₂ due to the presence of NO₂ group. Bromine has less -I effect than chlorine hence, the complex Zn(5-BrSal)₂ occupies the last position in the series of the stability order. The total energies of Zn^{II} complexes range from -4475.5903 to -3012.5885 eV (Table 1).

Table 1. Thermodynamic parameters for Zn^{II} complexes

Complex	Heat of formation (kcal)	Total energy (eV)	Ionization potential (eV)
Zn(sal)(5-ClSal)	-49.23077	-3313.98535	8.69643
Zn(sal)(5-BrSal)	-35.29408	-3350.62838	8.85759
Zn(sal)(5-NO ₂ sal)	-54.36585	-3744.11974	9.10797
Zn(5-ClSal)(5-BrSal)	-41.76737	-3652.02848	8.75946
Zn(5-ClSal)(5-NO ₂ sal)	-60.68261	-4045.51305	8.98398
Zn(5-BrSal)(5-NO ₂ sal)	-46.56326	-4082.14816	9.21086
Zn(sal) ₂	-42.83356	-3012.58855	8.76803
Zn(5-ClSal) ₂	-55.86615	-3615.39248	8.74240
Zn(5-BrSal) ₂	-27.69715	-3688.66572	8.97151
Zn(5-NO ₂ sal) ₂	-64.50169	-4475.59037	9.88501

Ionization potentials : The ionization potentials of Zn^{II} complexes are in the range 8.6964 to 9.8850 eV (Table 1). The ionization potential is highest for the com-

plex Zn(5-NO₂sal)₂ (9.8850 eV, Table 1), because in the NO₂ group the nitrogen atom is electronegative due to which it gives -I effect on benzene ring and simultaneously nitro group has double bond which is in conjugation with the double bonds of benzene ring, this creates resonance within the ring and gives -M effect. Both the effects lower the electron density in benzene ring and strongly deactivate the ring providing stability to the complex. Hence the ionization potential of the complex increases.

Atom electron densities and atomic charges : Atom electron densities give an idea about the coordination sites on the ligands through which the metal ions are bound. In the ligands salicylaldehyde, 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde, 5-bromosalicylaldehyde and 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde (Fig. 2) the atom electron densities on the oxygen atoms and carbon atoms of the carbonyl group are in the range 6.1934 to 6.2978 (Table 2) and 3.7799 to 4.2630 (Table 2) respectively. These data reveal that, due to high atom electron density on oxygen atoms, the metal ion will preferentially bind to oxygen atoms.

Fig. 2. Structure of salicylaldehyde and substituted salicylaldehydes.

Table 2. Atom electron densities for ligands

Ligand	O1	O5	C2	C3	C4
Salicylaldehyde (sal)	6.2143	6.2978	4.2076	3.8463	4.2303
5-Chlorosalicylaldehyde (5-Clisal)	6.2936	6.2061	4.2005	3.8405	4.2221
5-Bromosalicylaldehyde (5-Brsal)	6.2945	6.2052	4.2073	3.8329	4.2308
5-Nitrosalicylaldehyde (5-NO ₂ sal)	6.2873	6.1934	4.2395	3.7799	4.2630

In the Zn^{II} complexes atom electron densities on the oxygen atoms surrounding zinc are in the range 6.2550 to 6.3267 (Table 3) which do not differ significantly from those for the ligands. This may be due to the existence of similar type of ring in ligand due to hydrogen bonding.

During complex formation hydrogen is merely substituted by the metal ion. Atomic charges on the oxygen atoms surrounding zinc are -0.3267 to -0.2550 (Table 4).

Table 3. Atom electron densities on oxygen atoms of Zn^{II} complexes

Complex	O2	O3	O4	O5
Zn(sal)(5-Clisal)	6.3247	6.2659	6.2757	6.3242
Zn(sal)(5-Brsal)	6.3247	6.2649	6.2753	6.3227
Zn(sal)(5-NO ₂ sal)	6.3142	6.2550	6.2774	6.3216
Zn(5-Clisal)(5-Brsal)	6.3249	6.2649	6.2717	6.3205
Zn(5-Clisal)(5-NO ₂ sal)	6.3144	6.2553	6.2737	6.3191
Zn(5-Brsal)(5-NO ₂ sal)	6.3143	6.2555	6.2729	6.3192
Zn(sal) ₂	6.3267	6.2692	6.2748	6.3227
Zn(5-Clisal) ₂	6.3247	6.2654	6.2715	6.3203
Zn(5-Brsal) ₂	6.3251	6.2650	6.2712	6.3203
Zn(5-NO ₂ sal) ₂	6.3142	6.2562	6.2640	6.3106

Table 4. Atomic charges on oxygen atoms of Zn^{II} complexes

Complex	O2	O3	O4	O5
Zn(sal)(5-Clisal)	-0.324654	-0.265940	-0.275688	-0.324235
Zn(sal)(5-Brsal)	-0.324723	-0.264937	-0.275297	-0.322668
Zn(sal)(5-NO ₂ sal)	-0.314241	-0.255028	-0.277391	-0.321576
Zn(5-Clisal)(5-Brsal)	-0.324858	-0.264892	-0.271671	-0.320516
Zn(5-Clisal)(5-NO ₂ sal)	-0.314407	-0.255322	-0.273653	-0.319081
Zn(5-Brsal)(5-NO ₂ sal)	-0.314280	-0.255516	-0.272948	-0.319228
Zn(sal) ₂	-0.326703	-0.269221	-0.274830	-0.322692
Zn(5-Clisal) ₂	-0.324720	-0.265361	-0.271521	-0.320279
Zn(5-Brsal) ₂	-0.325055	-0.265020	-0.271229	-0.320316
Zn(5-NO ₂ sal) ₂	-0.314211	-0.256249	-0.263987	-0.310571

Geometry optimization :

Geometry optimization of mixed ligand and corresponding bis-complexes of Zn^{II} has been carried out and their bond lengths and bond angles have been calculated.

Bond lengths : The C-O and C=O bond lengths in ligands are in the range 1.3446 to 1.3639 Å (Table 5) and 1.2092 to 1.2200 Å (Table 5) respectively. In Zn^{II} complexes O-C bond distances between the oxygen atoms

Table 5. Bond lengths (Å) in ligands

Ligand	C2=O1	C4-O5
Salicylaldehyde (sal)	1.220036	1.354379
5-Chlorosalicylaldehyde (5-Clisal)	1.209297	1.363943
5-Bromosalicylaldehyde (5-Brsal)	1.209235	1.363443
5-Nitrosalicylaldehyde (5-NO ₂ sal)	1.218675	1.344680

Table 6. Bond lengths (Å) in Zn^{II} complexes

Complex	Ligand-I		Ligand-II		Ligand-I		Ligand-II	
	Zn1-O2	Zn1-O3	Zn1-O4	Zn1-O5	C6=O2	C8-O3	C11=O4	C9-O5
Zn(sal)(5-Clisal)	2.029541	1.957034	1.958626	2.029257	1.252978	1.300832	1.253292	1.298138
Zn(sal)(5-Brsal)	2.028484	1.960320	1.959382	2.036500	1.254085	1.298221	1.250613	1.295373
Zn(sal)(5-NO ₂ sal)	2.023999	1.951407	1.966374	2.036945	1.254351	1.300434	1.248761	1.295744
Zn(5-Clisal)(5-Brsal)	2.022267	1.965120	1.961955	2.028889	1.253686	1.297854	1.252538	1.296563
Zn(5-Clisal)(5-NO ₂ sal)	2.022078	1.953543	1.966583	2.038816	1.254503	1.300572	1.248006	1.289843
Zn(5-Brsal)(5-NO ₂ sal)	2.020477	1.952395	1.968770	2.033371	1.254560	1.299340	1.248061	1.289353
Zn(sal) ₂	2.021704	1.960914	1.966741	2.024366	1.254883	1.297041	1.254395	1.297824
Zn(5-Clisal) ₂	2.016191	1.969175	1.956797	2.059261	1.253830	1.296096	1.238754	1.303824
Zn(5-Brsal) ₂	2.027731	1.959209	1.958493	2.034600	1.252210	1.296451	1.250494	1.297152
Zn(5-NO ₂ sal) ₂	2.036945	1.966374	1.951407	2.023999	1.248761	1.295744	1.254351	1.300434

surrounding zinc and the carbon atoms attached to the respective oxygen atoms are in the range 1.2387 to 1.3038 Å (Table 6). Thus the values of C–O bond distances in Zn^{II} complexes are in between those of C–O and C=O bond lengths in ligands. This reveals the delocalization of the electrons. Zn–O bond lengths are in the range 1.951407 to 2.059261 Å (Table 6). These bond lengths are in good harmony with the X-ray crystal structure data of zinc complex of *N,N'*-bis(salicylidene)-3,6-dioxo-1,8-diaminooctane (ZnBSO.H₂O)¹⁸ in which Zn–O bond distances have been reported to be 1.932 Å and 1.949 Å.

Bond angles : O–Zn–O bond angles are close to 109.5° (100.095° to 116.680°, Table 7) supporting distorted tet-

rahedral geometry for the complexes. The 3D structures of Zn(5-Clisal)(5-NO₂sal), Zn(sal)(5-Brsal), Zn(5-Brsal)(5-NO₂sal) and Zn(5-Clisal)(5-Brsal) are given in Figs. 3–6.

Fig. 4. 3D-structure of Zn(sal)(5-Brsal).**Table 7.** O–Zn–O bond angles in Zn^{II} complexes

Complex	O2–Zn1–O4	O2–Zn1–O3	O2–Zn1–O5
Zn(sal)(5-Clisal)	109.09730	101.07924	110.00798
Zn(sal)(5-Brsal)	115.25051	100.92571	109.34974
Zn(sal)(5-NO ₂ sal)	108.81307	104.93702	113.20232
Zn(5-Clisal)(5-Brsal)	114.17530	102.65227	111.25244
Zn(5-Clisal)(5-NO ₂ sal)	111.04268	100.09544	111.17114
Zn(5-Brsal)(5-NO ₂ sal)	112.45362	101.75010	111.00456
Zn(sal) ₂	114.27689	100.66821	112.94981
Zn(5-Clisal) ₂	116.68055	108.95461	115.59349
Zn(5-Brsal) ₂	114.29252	112.95823	110.59731
Zn(5-NO ₂ sal) ₂	100.26332	100.24441	112.82501

rahedral geometry for the complexes. These bond angles are in accord with the X-ray crystal structure data of zinc complex of *N,N'*-bis(salicylidene)-3,6-dioxo-1,8-diaminooctane (ZnBSO.H₂O)¹⁸ in which O–Zn–O bond angles have been reported to be 117.36°. The 3D structures of Zn(5-

Data calculated by PM3 method on heats of formation, total energies and ionization potentials reveal the

Fig. 5. 3D-structure of Zn(5-Brsal)(5-NO₂sal).

Fig. 6. 3D-structure of Zn(5-Clsal)(5-Brsal).

thermodynamic stabilities of complexes. Atom electron densities and atomic charges confirm the coordination sites of the ligands for the metal ions. Geometry optimization revealing bond lengths and bond angles data support the distorted tetrahedral geometry of the complexes.

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